

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS

Aldashev Ilhomjon

Teacher of Fergana state university

Mamatqulova Shahzoda

Student of Fergana state university

Abstract: In the article, information technology's which are taught to students role in the teaching process, the achievements in this regard are analyzed.

Key words: information technology, online education, educational system, technical tools, sites.

In today's fast-paced era of globalization, individuals are interconnected and reliant on information technology like never before. It is almost impossible to envision a life devoid of technological tools, particularly those based on software. Many everyday objects that we use on software-based technologies that enhance their functionality and convenience. This demonstrates that information technology encompasses more than just computers and laptops; it extends to a wide range of devices that rely on software and technical components for their operation. The integration of information technology into various aspects of our lives has made tasks easier and more efficient, highlighting the indispensable role that technology plays in modern society.

The integration of information technology into the educational system has become a key component of state policy, emphasizing the necessity of utilizing technological tools in teaching and learning. Schools and universities are increasingly adopting modern educational practices that align with global standards, recognizing the significant impact of technology on enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in education. For instance, the gradual implementation of advanced computers and software in educational institutions across our country is a notable development. This

initiative aims to provide students with access to cutting-edge technology, expanding their horizons and equipping them with the latest knowledge and skills. By incorporating technology into the educational process, students are exposed to a diverse range of resources and learning opportunities that were previously inaccessible. This shift towards digital learning not only enhances the quality of education but also prepares students to navigate the complexities of the modern world. Through access to state-of-the-art tools and information, pupils and students are empowered to broaden their perspectives, stay abreast of current trends, and develop critical thinking skills necessary for success in today's rapidly evolving society. The integration of technology in education serves as a catalyst for fostering a generation of knowledgeable and well-equipped individuals who can thrive in an increasingly digitalized world.

In addition to traditional subjects, information technology tools are increasingly being integrated into school curriculum. These tools are not only used for practical work but also for demonstrating various processes, reactions, mechanical actions, and more through computer simulations. Computer science classes, considered crucial for students, prioritize the use of technology tools. The utilization of electronic boards in these classes aims to develop students' skills and proficiency in the field. An example of the integration of technology in education is the introduction of the kundalik.com application in schools in our country. This app serves as a platform for student evaluation and has become a valuable tool for both teachers and students to enhance their technological skills. Through this app, the evaluation process becomes more transparent, as personal biases are minimized. Overall, the incorporation of technology in education not only enhances traditional subjects but also provides opportunities for students to engage with modern tools and resources. By embracing technology in the classroom, students can develop essential skills needed to thrive in a digitalized world, ultimately preparing them for success in their academic and professional endeavors. State higher education institutions have made significant advancements in integrating technology into their classrooms, with each auditorium now equipped with televisions and specialized computers. Students are actively using

these technologies during practical and seminar classes, providing them with the opportunity to lead lessons themselves. This hands-on experience helps students develop the skills necessary to excel in their future careers. Similar to schools, universities have implemented an evaluation platform known as Hemis. This platform removes the human factor from the evaluation process, assessing students based on their task performance. Throughout this process, students are encouraged to conduct research, seek out information, and enhance their knowledge through direct communication with computers. By leveraging technology in higher education, students are not only gaining practical experience but also honing their research and communication skills. The integration of technology in classrooms is empowering students to take charge of their learning journey and equipping them with the tools needed to succeed in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the significant role of social network in teaching and learning. In teacher training, its main assistance was in creating opportunities for students to interact and communicate in various places. As a result, teaching has become more effective by using interesting technological tools or by teaching through the effective use of social networks. The integration of modern technologies in the education sector enhances its quality and simplifies the training of professionals who meet globally recognized standards. Consequently, the significance of information technology tools in this field is substantial and increasingly crucial as methods evolve and progress to become a profession.

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